

EXPLORING THE CORRELATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (TPACK) OF B.ED STUDENTS WITH THEIR SELF-EFFICACY AND TEACHING ATTITUDE

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Paper Received On: 21 October 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 25 November 2025

Published On: 01 December 2025

Abstract

A teacher is expected to have the knowledge of pedagogy along with the knowledge of content and ICT integration. Moreover self-efficacy and a positive attitude towards teaching also matter. The present study aims to investigate the correlation of Technological, Pedagogical and Content knowledge of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy and Teaching attitude. Simple Random Sampling Technique is used to select 560 B.Ed students as a sample. Descriptive Survey Method is employed. The tools adopted for this study are TPACK Scale developed and standardized by Prof. Hemant Lata Sharma & Ms. Leena Sharma; Self-efficacy Scale developed and standardized by Dr.Arun Kumar Singh & Dr. Shruti Narain and Teaching Attitude Scale developed and standardized by Nasrin and Komy Biswas to collect data. The findings revealed a significant correlation between TPACK and Self-efficacy of but no correlation between TPACK and Teaching attitude of B.Ed students.

Keywords: TPACK, Self-efficacy, Teaching attitude, B.Ed students, Assam.

INTRODUCTION:

Schulman in 1987 mentioned that a teacher should possess two kinds of basis knowledge i.e., pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge (PCK). Koehler and Mishra in 2006 introduced the framework TPACK (Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge)

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suggesting that along with PCK a teacher should have the knowledge of ICT integration to optimize students' learning outcome. This framework focuses on the essential knowledge domains required for a teacher to transact the curriculum effectively.

Pre-service teacher education (like B.Ed, D.El.Ed) is expected to inculcate TPACK competency among trainees as these trainees are in their beginning stage of teaching profession. Along with this, developing self-efficacy as well as teaching attitude among these prospective teachers is also expected from such training programme. Self-efficacy is the beliefs of an individual about his capabilities of doing or managing a task well and teaching attitude is the perception and values of an individual (teacher) towards his teaching profession.

Many studies have revealed that pre-service teacher having strong self-efficacy and a positive teaching attitude towards teaching are more likely to adopt innovative strategies along with ICT integration. However, we need to explore whether TPACK knowledge have direct influence on these two dimensions, i.e., self-efficacy and teaching attitude of prospective teachers. And it is crucial to understand this relation for teacher education institutions to adopt (if needed) such curriculum design and interventions that inculcate both technological knowledge and affective readiness among prospective teachers.

Therefore, the present study aims to explore and examine whether TPACK, self-efficacy and teaching attitude of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam are correlated to each other. This will help developing a deeper insight for enhancing teacher education programmes in the context of 21st century.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PRESENT STUDY:

- (1) To study the relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy.
- (2) To study the relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching Attitude.
- (3) To study the relationship between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching Attitude.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESIS:

Research Questions:

- (1) Is there any relationship between TPACK among B.Ed students and their Self-efficacy?

- (2) Is there any relationship between TPACK among B.Ed students and their attitude towards teaching?
- (3) Is there any relationship between Self-efficacy among B.Ed students and their Teaching attitude?

Research Hypotheses:

- (1) There is no significant relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students and their Self-efficacy.
- (2) There is no significant relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of and their Teaching attitude.
- (3) There is no significant relationship between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students and their Teaching attitude.

METHODOLOGY:

Descriptive survey method is employed by the researchers to collect data.

POPULATION:

The population for this study comprises of 1150 students studying in 12 private B.Ed colleges of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam.

SAMPLE:

The researchers have adopted Simple Random Sampling Technique to select 560 B.Ed trainees (280 students from Kamrup (Metro) district's B.Ed Colleges and 280 students from Kamrup district's B.Ed Colleges) from 8 private B.Ed Colleges affiliated to Gauhati University of both Kamrup(Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam as a sample for the study.

TOOLS USED:

The researchers have adopted the following 3 tools for conducting the present study:

- (1) Teachers' Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge Scale (TTPACKS-SHSL) developed and standardized by Prof. Hemant Lata Sharma and Ms. Leena Sharma (2017).
- (2) Self-efficacy Scale (SES-SANS) developed and standardized by Dr.Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain (2014).
- (3) Teaching Attitude Scale (TAS-NBK) developed and standardized by Nasrin and Komy Biswas (2024).

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA:**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TPACK OF B.ED STUDENTS OF KAMRUP (METRO) AND KAMRUP DISTRICTS OF ASSAM AND THEIR SELF-EFFICACY:**

In order to determine relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy, product moment coefficient of correlation is used.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy.

Table-1: Relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students and their Self-efficacy

Variables	Mean	SD	Sample	df	Coefficient of Correlation (r)	Significance
TPACK	225.8	17.88	560	558	0.206	Significant at 0.05 level
SELF-EFFICACY	76.38	7.69				

The above table-1 shows that the calculated value of 'r' between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy is 0.206, which is greater than the tabulated value of 'r' (0.062) at 0.05 level for 558 df. Hence, the hypothesis that "There is no significant relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy" is rejected at 0.05 level. This indicates that there is a significant correlation between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TPACK OF B.ED STUDENTS OF KAMRUP (METRO) AND KAMRUP DISTRICTS OF ASSAM AND THEIR TEACHING ATTITUDE:

In order to determine relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude, product moment coefficient of correlation is used.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude.

Table-2: Relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students and their Teaching attitude:

Variables	Mean	SD	Sample	df	Coefficient of Correlation (r)	Significance
TPACK	225.8	17.88	560	558	-0.003	Not significant at 0.05 level
TEACHING ATTITUDE	159.71	9.78				

The above table-2 shows that the calculated value of 'r' between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude is -0.003, which is smaller than the tabulated value of 'r' (0.062) at 0.05 level for 558 df. Hence, the hypothesis that "There is no significant relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude" is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant correlation between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-EFFICACY OF B.ED STUDENTS OF KAMRUP (METRO) AND KAMRUP DISTRICTS OF ASSAM AND THEIR TEACHING ATTITUDE:

In order to determine relationship between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude, product moment coefficient of correlation is used.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude.

Table-3: Relationship between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students and their Teaching attitude

Variables	Mean	SD	Sample	df	Coefficient of Correlation (r)	Significance
TEACHING ATTITUDE	159.71	9.78	560	558	0.101	Significant at 0.05 level
SELF-EFFICACY	76.38	7.69				

The above table-3 shows that the calculated value of 'r' between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude is

0.101, which is greater than the tabulated value of 'r' (0.062) at 0.05 level for 558 df. Hence, the hypothesis that "There is no significant relationship between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude" is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is a significant correlation between Self-efficacy of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Teaching attitude.

FINDINGS OF THE PRESENT STUDY:

(1) Relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy:

Significant correlation is found between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy.

(2) Relationship between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their teaching attitude:

No significant correlation is found between TPACK of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their teaching attitude.

(3) Relationship between Teaching attitude of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy:

Significant correlation is found between teaching attitude of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their Self-efficacy.

CONCLUSION:

This study was an attempt to reveal a clear picture of the relationship between technological, pedagogical and content knowledge of B.Ed students of Kmarup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam and their self-efficacy as well as teaching attitude.

The researchers studied the level of TPACK with the help of Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Scale developed and standardized by Prof. Hemant Lata Sharma and Ms. Leena Sharma, self-efficacy with the help of Self-efficacy Scale (SES) developed and standardized by Dr.Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain and Teaching Attitude Scale developed and standardized by Nasrin and Komy Biswas.

The researchers examined that there is an association between TPACK of B.Ed students with their self-efficacy but no such association was found between TPACK and teaching attitude of B.Ed students. Moreover, an association was found between self-efficacy and teaching attitude of B.Ed students of Kamrup (Metro) and Kamrup districts of Assam.

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